

Navigating social sustainability and supply chain resilience: a preliminary research on the actions to face current global challenges

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Abstract

Purpose

Currently, supply chains (SC) are facing specific social challenges, e.g. demographic changes which, for instance, create new consumption patterns. Although these challenges are making SCs more vulnerable, they create opportunities to transform SCs towards sustainability. Under this scenario, SCs need to develop actions for enhancing SC resilience (SCRES) and moving towards sustainability. However, despite these implications, the research on this field is still in its infancy (Carissimi, et al. 2023).

This study aims to analyze which actions support the development of resilience and sustainability. As a preliminary study, it focuses particularly on the actions that favor the development of social sustainability and SCRES. In addition, several synergies and trade-offs between the actions, SCRES capabilities, and sustainability dimensions have been identified.

Design/methodology/approach

To answer the research question, i.e. which actions support the development of social sustainability and SCRES, the authors analysed the state-of-the-art on resilience and sustainability. This allows to identify the framework for the analysis. To identify the actions that support social sustainability, the authors adopted the definition of Gimenez et al. (2012), while they referred to the classification of SCRES capabilities of Chowdhury and Quaddus (2017).

Then, they carried out a review (Tranfield et al., 2003) starting from the main social challenges and/or the related risks that SCs are facing and placed them in the identified framework. They use this exemplary string in Scopus:

(TITLE-ABS-KEY ("name-of-social-challenges" OR "name-of-social-challenges-related-risk") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ("supply chain" OR "value chain"))

Finally, during a workshop attended by European experts from industry and academia, several synergies and trade-offs effects of the identified actions on different SCRES capabilities, and sustainability dimensions were identified.

Figure 1 shows the research framework.

Figure 1. Research framework.

Findings

The findings reveal how SCs can increase their SCRES and social sustainability through specific actions. Moreover, several synergies and trade-offs between SCRES capabilities and sustainability dimensions were identified through the workshop. The following action is given as an example:

- Engage SC actors to ensure good practices from end to end of the SCs (e.g.: increase vigilance and pressure on suppliers, forcing an end to child labour through wholesale pricing)

The implementation of this action has a positive effect on visibility and social sustainability; however, it can generate a negative impact on economic sustainability and flexibility because it makes supply chains less flexible in supplier selection.

Practical implications

The study provides a tool for practitioners that, according to the specific challenge they are coping with, can analyse how to increase SCRES and social sustainability through specific actions answering to current global challenges.

Relevance/contribution

The great pressure that global challenges put on the business world is pushing SCs to implement SCRES and sustainability. However, there is still a limited understanding of which actions could effectively result in an improvement in resilience and sustainability (Negri et al., 2022). This preliminary study contributes to this existing conversation. Focussing on the social challenges SCs are facing, this research identifies from the literature the actions that develop SCRES and social sustainability. Then, shedding light on possible synergies and trade-offs, it lays foundations for future research on the relationship between SCRES and sustainability.

Keywords: Social sustainability, Supply chain resilience, social challenges

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